

LINGUISTIC MEANS OF REPRESENTATION OF THE "HOSPITALITY" CONCEPT IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LINGUOCULTURES

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Abstract: The article is devoted to the representation of the concept "hospitality" in Russian and English linguocultures and is based on the generally recognized provisions of conceptology. The authors refer to the content of the concept "concept", consider the structure of the concept and ways of its representation. Admitting a certain unprovability of the conceptological theory, the authors note its connection with the cognitive aspect. At the same time, referring to the traditional ways of verbalization of the mental formation allows to build the structure of the concept and determine its content. The most culturally significant aspects of the concept "hospitality" are discussed, it is noted that most of its components are axiologically loaded.

Keywords: concept, linguistic means of representation, structure, concept "hospitality"

Introduction: The present study is devoted to the study of linguistic representation of the concept "hospitality" in English and Russian linguocultures. The chosen concept has a universal nature and is insufficiently studied in the linguistic aspect. At the same time its socio-cultural significance is rather high. This concept is a significant unit for all cultures. In the light of its connection with ethnological traditions, moreover, it gives an understanding of the cultural picture of a certain ethnic group.

In Soviet times, there was a peculiar gradation within the country among the peoples of the USSR. Some of them were considered the most hospitable, for example, the inhabitants of the Transcaucasus. Others, such as the Baltic peoples, were considered less hospitable. It should be emphasized that these perceptions were nothing but stereotypes. However, it is the stereotypes that play a great role in the formation of everyday consciousness and cultural picture of the world. Scientific concepts are conceptualized according to objective grounds, while everyday concepts are conceptualized according to stereotypical models. Stereotyped notions of English inhospitality are reflected, for example, in the following words: "The English is considered by many foreigners to be inhospitable and cold. This is due the fact that the English may treat you coldly and will not talk about anything with a stranger. However, when you submit a letter of recommendation. The English will be very cordial with you. They will introduce you to the family circle, and after a while, they will behave with you quite frankly." [1].

In connection with the importance of hospitality as a social and cultural phenomenon. The question arises about the ways of representation of the concept "hospitality" in two different linguistic cultures - Russian and English.

The relevance of this research is due to the increased interest in the description of the language picture of the world from the scientific point of view and, in particular, in the social aspects of linguistic behavior. On the other hand, the relevance of the topic is determined by the insufficient study of the chosen concept and constant diachronic changes of its content.

The object of the research in the present work is the linguocultural "hospitality" concept as a part of human worldview. The subject is similarities and differences in linguistic description

of the concept "hospitality" in Russian and English languages.

The aim of the research is to study and describe the concept "hospitality" in two linguocultures - English and Russian.

The specified goal is achieved by solving the following tasks:

- define the content of the concept of the concept;
- to consider linguistic ways of representation of the concept;
- identify the main linguocultural content of the concept "hospitality" in Russian and English linguocultures.

The novelty of the research consists in the treatment of the concept "hospitality" from the linguocultural approach and in the consideration of the linguistic means of its representation. The topic of our article is close to the PhD thesis of G.R. Garipova, however, the material of the research there is only phraseological expressions.

Theoretical significance of the work lies in the consideration of theoretical aspects of the study of the concept as a linguocultural formation. Some aspects of the term "concept" are clarified. It is offered to distinguish verifiable and non-verifiable interpretations of the concept. This method can be applied in further study of ways of linguistic representation of concepts in comparative aspect.

The practical significance consists in the possible use of the results of practical significance consists in possible use of research results in linguodidactic purposes, namely in translation practice, in the preparation of courses of lectures on lexicology and intercultural communication.

The theoretical basis of the study consists of the works of a number of scientists - linguists and linguoculturalists: I.A. Sternin, Z.D. Popova, E.S. Kubryakova, G.G. Slyshkin, V.I. Karasik, L.G. Babenko and others.

The material for the study was the data of explanatory, etymological, monolingual and bilingual dictionaries, as well as dictionaries of synonyms and antonyms in English and Russian.

Let's consider the concept "concept". A concept is understood as the key aspect of linguocultural studies, carrying in itself "a multilevel mental formation, lying in consciousness, language and culture". [2, c. 324].

According to A.S. Askoldov, the concept is a mental formation, a kind of substitute for a variety of objects of the same kind [3, p. 269]. S.A. Askoldov singles out artistic concepts in this work - "concepts of cognition of the common, concepts of art are individual". [4, p. 91]. In addition, he describes the relationship between concepts and their processes, attributing to them the process of categorization of information, which is "the allocation of some minimal units of human experience in their ideal meaningful representation" [5, p. 93].

D.S. Likhachev points out: the concept is separate in every dictionary meaning of a word, moreover, it is "a kind of algebraic expression meaning, which we operate with in written and oral speech, for one simply has no time to grasp the meaning in all its complexity, sometimes cannot, and sometimes interprets it in his own way" [6, 3-4]. Here D.S. Likhachev combines two different approaches to the concept - logical "algebraic" and pragmatic. These two interpretations go back to the dispute between H.W. Leibniz and J. Locke. Locke believed that man singles out those features of an object "to which he cares most... If a man applies signs to things unknown to him, he makes them sound without meaning." [7]. Leibniz, on the contrary,

insisted that the structure and composition of a concept do not depend on human arbitrariness and include all components, both known and unknown to us. It is necessary to distinguish between scientific concepts and everyday meaning.

The actual meaning of a concept may not coincide with its logical composition. This relevance is determined by the totality of the associative series, including both personal and socio-cultural experience of a person. "If a concept in the form of an associative series, then the nominant of this series N.S. Bolotnova points out in her studies [8].

Concepts possess universality, without this generality communication process is impossible. Each concept can be decoded differently depending on a momentary context and cultural experience, cultural individuality of a concept-carrier [6, p. 4-10].

A concept is signified and, besides, it has a possibility to be expressed verbally, hence, through language, and also nonverbal, that is other ways of transfer of this or that material, information, for example, drawing [5, p. 128-130].

M.V. Pimenova understands a concept as a representation of a part of the world or even a certain part of the world, which has a complex structure, expressed by a number of features, which are realized with the use of linguistic ways and means [9, p. 24]. The structure of a concept is characterized by features, functionally significant for a certain culture.

Within the framework of the semantic-cognitive approach the concept is given such definition as an accessory of human consciousness, a global unit of thinking activity". [10, c. 19]. A concept is "a discrete mental formation, a basic unit of the human thinking code that has a relatively ordered internal structure that is the result of cognitive (cognitive) activity of the individual and society and carrying complex, encyclopedic information about the reflected subject or phenomenon, about the interpretation of this information by public consciousness and the attitude of public consciousness to this phenomenon or object". [10, 34].

According to S.G. Vorkachev, within linguocultural research a "concept" is "a unit of collective knowledge/consciousness (referring to higher spiritual values), which has a language expression and is marked by ethnocultural specificity" [11, 70].

V.I. Karasik considers the concept of language as a primary cultural formation and expression of the objective content of words that have a certain meaning. Therefore, they are transmitted to many spheres of human life, "in particular to the spheres of predominantly conceptual (science), predominantly figurative (art) and predominantly active (everyday life) world perception of the world" [12, p. 123]. The author's structure emphasizes the figurative-perceptual component, the conceptual component, namely the information-factual component, and value component, that is, evaluation and behavioral norms [12, p. 118].

S. Stepanov, who studied the concept of the concept, argues that "the concept is a "blob of culture" in human consciousness". The scientist believes that the concept is cell of culture in the mental world of man, that is the form in which the culture of a certain nation penetrates the mental environment of the human being and directly that by which and man enters into the culture or even has the culture of a particular human being is that which penetrates into the mental environment of the human being or even has the opportunity to influence it, without being a "creator of cultural values" [13, 43].

Z.D. Popova and I.A. Sternin cite three basic structural components of a concept, namely - image, informational content and interpretational field. The first is peculiar to both words that denote those or other objects and abstract vocabulary. The sensual image in the structure of

the concept carries perceptual signs produced with the help of the sense organs. As well as figurative signs arising by means of metaphorical comprehension of this or that object or phenomenon [10, p. 108-109]. According to Z.D. Popova, "the informational content of a concept includes a minimum of cognitive attributes defining the basic, most important distinctive features of a specific object or phenomenon" [10, p. 109]. The interpretative field of a concept contains also cognitive features interpreting in a certain plan "the basic informational content of the concept, derive from it, representing some inference knowledge, or evaluate it" [20, p. 109], and evaluative, encyclopedic, utilitarian, regulatory, socio-cultural, paremiological zones [10, p. 110-112].

Following O.E. Bepalova, the definitions of cultural and artistic concepts, based on the following parameters:

- "connection with the forms of speech/non-speech artistic thinking;
- orientation in relation to the concept sphere of literature as a subsystem of orientation in relation to the whole mental space of culture;
- redistribution of nuclear and peripheral features in the content of the concept in different poets / stable correlation of the core and periphery of the concept in the consciousness of an average native speaker;
- decoding the content of the concept on the basis of artistic/cultural presupposition". [14, c. 6].

L.G. Babenko notes: the structure of the concept carries in itself the nuclear-field organization and singles out in it:

- core, which represents the basic cognitive-propositional structure;
- the nearer zone - basic lexical representations;
- the immediate periphery - nominatively combined and associative-imaginative representations;
- further periphery - subjective-modal, emotional and evaluative meanings [15, p. 111].

The fundamental cognitive-propositional connection is "the connection revealed by means of generalization of real contexts, textual proposition in the form of the argument-predicate structure, represented in this text (or a set of texts of one author)". [15, p. 110-111].

Both textual and intertextual associative and semantic fields of concepts are studied in the communicative stylistic coloring of the text. The structure of the text associative and semantic field of the concept:

- 1) the core - it includes the key word- nominative of the concept and synonymous to it lexical units of word and superword types;
- 2) periphery, which consists of various representatives - applicators and actualizers of the concept. Concept representers "express the concept encoded in the text, being a form of its materialization", and actualizers "serve as additional markers of concepts, reinforcing their textual representation". [16, c. 75]. In the case when the word nominative of the unit concept is absent, its textual associative and semantic fields can be modified into nuclear, "from the point of view of the associative deployment of the text, the representants and actualizers are stimuli - elements of the lexical structure of the text, generating associations" [8, p. 75]. [8, c. 75]. An associative is "an element of the lexical structure of the text that is correlated in the mind of the subject perceiving the text with the realities of the text world, correlating with the world of reality; consciousness as well as with other words" [8, c. 72]. Text associations form a

whole associative series, as they themselves connect within the same kind of association [8, p. 75].

A concept is a mental unit located in the human consciousness and has many dimensions. The main feature of a concept is its content. A concept has its own structure, and also includes not only a set of features of an object, but also those associations and feelings, representations and knowledge, which are caused by the given object. To a greater extent, the concept is reflected in the written form in linguocultural texts. In them concepts are "objectified", "absorb the generalized content of many forms of expression", "are filled with meanings" and so on [11, p. 67].

Linguistics also presents a group of authors who do not accept the concept of "concept". Thus, in the work of Y.V. Fomenko it is noted: "Cognitive linguistics does not need the term concept. The cognitive linguistics does not need the term "concept" and can "get along" with the traditional, general scientific term "concept". And the term concept should be used as its synonym. So-called conceptology contradicts numerous facts of language and speech, fundamental provisions of linguistics, psycholinguistics and philosophy, the requirements of objectivity and proof". [18, p. 122].

Summing up our cursory review of different views on the concept of "concept", we can say the following: first, the term "concept" is significantly broader than the term "concept". A concept includes only logical and minimal semantic components. A concept also includes associative elements of various types, connotations, which from the logical point of view can be considered redundant. Despite this, there is nothing in conceptology that contradict the fundamental "facts of language and speech", the provisions of "psycholinguistics and philosophy" [18, p. 122].

However, it should be recognized that there is indeed some part of conceptual theory that lies beyond provability. These are mainly cognitive aspects of the theory. It is possible to collect numerous circumstantial proofs that some concept, e.g. "hospitality", exists as a frame, script, or gestalt, but irrefutable evidence for the existence of frames or gestalts in the mind or subconscious really doesn't exist. This is why there are several interpretations of the term "concept." Their interchangeability shows that, unfortunately, none of the theories is entirely unsatisfactory precisely for the reasons we have outlined above. Therefore, the discussion of concepts can be considered precisely an argument about terms and not about substance. The concept as a linguocognitive and linguocultural unit is a pragmatically convenient, intuitively acceptable object of research. We believe that such structuring of language and hypostasis of the corresponding picture of the world is quite justified. Let's go to now directly to the analysis of the concept "hospitality" in Russian and English languages.

This article does not claim to be a complete and comprehensive analysis of the concept "hospitality." It presents individual components of the analysis. A full-fledged analysis of the concept includes several obligatory stages:

1. Etymological analysis.
2. Lexicographic analysis. Definitional and semantic analysis.
3. Combinatorial analysis.
4. Phraseological analysis.
5. Textual analysis. It may also include analysis of speech situations, such as inviting, welcoming guests, table talk, saying goodbye to guests, and so on.

6. Structural analysis. The final results can be presented in the form of charts and tables.
7. System analysis, that is, the relationship of a given concept to others, intersection of concepts, hypo- or hyperonymic connections, and so on.
8. An associative experiment.
9. Corpus analysis. Items 8-9 can be considered optional, but desirable.

In this article we will touch upon stages 1-5. In this article, we will address systems analysis only as necessary. For example, the concept "hospitality" is certainly included in such macro-concepts as "man", "home", "friendship - enmity", "one's own - another's". A detailed analysis of this multifaceted complex structure is the subject of a large, voluminous study. Here we will touch upon only the most culturally significant aspects of the concept of hospitality. In addition, in the semantic, stylistic and textual it is important to distinguish the types of components of the concept. They can be either neutral or axiologically, stylistically, emotionally loaded.

We will see that most of the components of the studied concept are axiologically loaded, that is, hospitality is positive, moral, socially approved and encouraged behavior. Let us turn to the consideration of the concept "hospitality", which, following V.A. Maslova's classification, it is possible to refer to the category of social concepts and relations due to the fact that hospitality as a phenomenon is considered only within a society with a specific culture and history [20]. Nomination of the concept "hospitality" according to the explanatory dictionaries of the Russian language is a derivative word from the adjective hospitable and is defined by such synonyms as hospitable, cordiality. The latter lexeme is etymologically formed from the word joyfulness by means of haplology, which bears the result of the fusion of the roots of the words "rad" and "soul". The word хлебосољство was formed from the phraseology of bread and salt, which means a symbolic treat.

For the Russian culture is symbolic, formed from this phrase "хлебосољство", as well as related words: "хлебосољ" or "хлебосољство", characterizing in the Russian consciousness the generosity and generosity and openness. A joint meal, a treat is a universal ritual of welcoming guest. "Breaking bread" is a biblical symbol of peace, acceptance into one's circle. Bread is the main element and symbol of satiation in many cultures, with the exception of "rice" or "corn." "Bread and salt" is apparently a uniquely Russian combination, a lingvoculture, according to V.V. Vorobyov, that is, "khlebsol - baked goods as a Russian custom and one of the characteristic features of the Russian national character" [19, c. 114].

From the position of cultural values and ethnological traits hospitality represents a fragment of the autostereotype of the Russian people. The core lexeme "hospitality" in Russian linguoculture has the ability to create polysemic expressions with adjectives that have become derivatives of ethnonyms, namely, with the connotation of Russian hospitality. Such word combinations can be accompanied by various tropes, such word combinations can be accompanied by different tropes, such as epithets to express generalization and marking of hospitality as a national trait: "glorified", "famous", "traditional" that is a phraseological term - "Russian traditional hospitality".

As derivatives of the adjective name of the word "hospitable" the following lexemes should be added: "most hospitable," "most hospitable," "hospitable," "inhospitable", "prehospitable." [21].

"Considering the fact that word formation is the result of the creative activity of human

consciousness in the process of cognition and leads to the expansion of the conceptual structure of the word, let us turn to the analysis word-formation nest of the lexeme "guest" in the Russian language" [21].

In the languages of the Slavic peoples the lexeme "guest" rather early began to characterize a visiting merchant. "Гостиные дворы" of Russian cities is a confirmation of this. Over time, the word was modified lexically into "visitor-friend," such concepts as "hospitality" and "living room" appeared: any memory of the "enemy visitor" dissolved. Over time, the meanings of the words were replaced by completely opposite ones [21].

It is also necessary to touch upon the word-formation aspect, within which we can distinguish the following morphological units, mostly affixes, which are means of conceptualizing new meanings: on-,for-, over-, form a new semantics "abuse of hospitality" - to distribute, to over distribute; morphemes you-, denote "completion of action" - to distribute; morphemes pre-, to-, most-; have the coloring of "degree of hospitality" - most hospitable.

The antonyms analysis, given above, leads to the following conclusion: in Russian the term "hospitality" is contrasted with the features of "inhospitable host," including the characterization of him as spiteful, greedy, even avaricious person.

If we speak about the lexeme hospitality in Russian, it is characterized by the following predicative combination: to show, to render, to show (hospitality). To express one or another action, such as paying attention or to show hospitality the verbs "to oblige" are common in Russian, "bother", "bow", "to feed", "to drink", "to sit down", "to bring," "welcome," "to feast," "to kiss," "to welcome," "to dine", "to please", "to respect".

Language is not so much a reflection of the world as of its cultural component, as it shapes the mentality of its speakers. This axiom opens up completely new parameters of nationality as a social concept. Nationality is not only a blood bond, genetic features or ethnic traits, but also the relation to the native language and native culture, because as it is with the help of language and cultural aspect both the personality is formed, and national character [22, p. 189].

The concept "hospitality" is analyzed from the point of view of the national and linguistic picture of the world of a certain ethnic group. This approach singles out one of the most important aspects of culture - etiquette, which is its phenomenon, covering the whole range of human feelings and emotions, and enriches the relationship between people.

"Etiquette is one of the pronounced phenomena of culture, which affects the whole gamut of human feelings and emotions and enriches human communication itself. The role of etiquette in society has always been very great, which is confirmed by its long historical and social evolution, functions in society, a multidimensional structure, 88 diverse types and forms. Unlike ritual, the ritual ceremonies of which are demonstrative etiquette is based on practical social expediency. The most important feature of etiquette is also the fact that it is always subordinate to the existing system of cultural values. To accept the etiquette norms is to recognize oneself as a member of a given social group or society as a whole and to submit to the cultural values established there" [23]. "Hospitality may be inherent in different peoples, but hospitality is always perceived as a specifically Russian trait" [24, 161-162].

Hospitality is a permanent feature, which is a property not so much of a person as much as of a family or even a nation, its manifestations are in love, care and constant readiness to receive guests: the house of such a person is always open for others, the host tries to create

comfortable conditions for their stay, "it is supposed to treat the guest or provide shelter, a bed for a long time" [16, 115]. It is a cordial, sincere and joyful reception of guests, as well as gratuitous not only regarding the reception, but also the treats.

In Russian culture it is customary to prepare as much food and drink as possible, even if the host understands in advance that it is impossible for even the hungriest guest to eat that much food. On the one hand, this on the one hand, it demonstrates the well-being of the host and, on the other hand, the special position of the guest.

The word "hospitality" was formed from the lexemes "guest" and "receive". There was a tradition that has survived to our times, namely, it has long been customary for hosts to tidy up the appearance - their own and home, to prepare treats and gifts, to welcome guests with bread and salt, moreover, guests were seated in the "red" corner, as this place was considered the most honorable in the house.

Thus, in the Russian linguistic culture the concept "hospitality" is associated with hospitality, refreshment, hospitality and unselfishness. Hospitality was the most ancient virtue in many cultures. In contemporary Russian culture is characterized by less ritualization and low formalization, especially among the younger generation.

In English, according to the dictionary [27], the word "hospitality" came from from Old French *hospitalité* - "hospitality"; from Latin *hospitalitem* - "friendliness to guests". In English, there are many synonyms of the word "hospitable": "friendly", "companionable", "sociable", "neighbourly", "cordial", "kind", "gregarious". [27, c. 189].

The lexeme "hospitable" - "hospitable" is opposed by antonyms, signs of an inhospitable person: "greedy", "unfriendly", "stingy with treats", "evil".

Frequent word combinations with the word "hospitality" (to give hospitality, to show hospitality, to offer hospitality, to extend hospitality) imply the act of presenting a gift, as well as attentive and respectful treatment of guest. In addition, in English the manifestation of hospitality is expressed in a number of phraseological expressions, for example, to give somebody a hospitable welcome, to play host.

M. Bakhtin completes the series by singling out the following concepts associated with the concept of "hospitality": "guest", "hospitable person", "receiving guest" [25, p. 27].

There are many idioms in the English language, which give an idea of the English picture of hospitality. For example, to break bread with somebody - to enjoy hospitality; too keep a good house - a table; to treat guests well, to have a good kitchen; keep open doors/ keep the doors open - to be always ready to receive guests; to live in grand style; to welcome guests; to be distinguished by hospitality; bread-and-butter letter, meaning a letter of thanks for hospitality, written after visiting someone's home; thanks letter.

However, there are some English proverbs with negative attitudes toward guests, such as those who linger with their hosts. One of them is "the best fish smell when they are three days old" ("after three days even the best fish begins to smell bad"). There are also other themes in this vein, for example, the English proverb "eat at pleasure, drink with measure," on the contrary, urges not to get carried away in drinking alcohol [26].

A guest is "someone who is staying in someone else's home because they have been invited". [26, p. 105.]. In addition, a guest is characterized by such qualities such as "important", "pleasant", "welcome", "dear". Relevant in this matter the saying "welcome as flowers in May", which refers to pleasant, unexpected guests. This phrase times shows a positive attitude

toward any guest at any time.

There are a number of adjectives in English that are associated with the concept of "hospitality," namely, "sociable," "companionable," "friendly," "kind", "generous", etc. Moreover, the lexemes "bread and salt" as the English consider these products as a sign of respect for the guest. Some more examples: as I live by bread (as a word of honor); break bread with somebody (to share food); by bread and salt ("bread and salt"). I swear to God! (the old oath); eat (take) bread and salt; eat somebody's bread and salt (to be somebody's guest) [25].

There are several sayings about the host who welcomes guests: "to keep a good house" - to have everything ready for a visiting guest, "to keep open house" - to make any guest feel important and welcome, "to play host" - to treat guests well. In addition, there are such sayings as "to give at homes," "to give a hospitable welcome," "give the red-carpet treatment," and "to give a lighted candle", which means a friendly and good attitude towards the guest.

Based on the analysis of phraseology, the concept "hospitality" in English has the following elements:

1) hospitality of hosts: the reception should be warm and cordial, the host tries to do everything so that the guest would feel at home. However, the host may pretend to be hospitable toward the guest, who stays longer than he should.

Example: to give a guest the red-carpet treatment;

2) invitation to the table: this aspect plays an important role in showing hospitality.

Examples: dinner is served; enjoy your meal;

3) a generous meal: it shows the host's good attitude towards the host;

Examples: be my guest; help yourself;

4) commitment to tradition: the English have several dining habits;

Examples: five o' clock tea (afternoon tea in England), the flitch of Dun - mow (serving smoked pork to a guest);

5) guest gratitude: the guest shows respect for warm hospitality.

Examples: bread and butter letter; "I had a great time" (before leaving home);

6) seeing the guest off: the host always helps the guest out of the house.

Examples: "We're glad you could come" / "We're glad that you dropped by."

English traditions have a great influence on the culture of this nation because they go deep into history. The commitment to tradition is one of the most striking characteristics of the English people, which is expressed in all walks of life, from politics - the power of the royal family - to the five o'clock tea party.

Every concept relies on precedent texts. The concept we are studying concept is based on texts talking about hospitality, the need to feed the hungry and shelter the homeless. The common source of such texts for Christian is the Bible:

Luke 14: 12 Then Jesus said to his host, "When you give a luncheon or dinner, do not invite your friends, your brothers or sisters, your relatives, or your rich neighbors; If you do, they may invite you back and so you will be repaid. 13 But when you give a banquet, invite the poor, the crippled, the lame, the blind, 14 and you will be blessed. Although they cannot repay you, you will be repaid at the resurrection of the righteous."

Much attention is paid to food because it is part of British hospitality. Despite the British respect for foreign cuisine, they still prefer the English breakfast of bacon or sausages,

scrambled eggs, and fried tomatoes. It is worth adding that every dinner includes the traditional English pudding. There is a tradition of "five o'clock" tea, after which the British can switch to stronger drinks. These traditions are now mostly tourist attractions.

"Home" is one of the main concepts of English culture, as the English honor family traditions. There is a saying "An Englishman's house is his castle," which reflects the strength of the traditions of the English people, the English "lead a secluded lifestyle, close to the family in their home". [17, c. 103].

We have already pointed out that the phraseological aspect of the concept "hospitality" has been previously studied by G.R. Garipova, so we will only touch briefly on the phraseology. We will give only a few examples, noting that in English phrases are used much less frequently than in Russian. Not all phrases are part of the core of the concept, and some, perhaps, are unknown to the average English speaker.

The very reception of guests and their treating is related to the English culture of food and drinks. Among the phraseological units and cultures that were analyzed, we can distinguish the following groups:

- 1) phraseological units with references to national food and alcohol. Examples: hot dog ("hot dog"); shepherd's pie (potato casserole); small bear (low-alcohol beer); dog's nose (a mixture of beer and gin);
- 2) idioms, sayings, and proverbs that reflect the culture of eating and drinking. Examples: drink off the candle-ends (to drink a volley to the bottom), sire that cheer, but not inebriate (a drink that makes you feel good, but not intoxicating (tea);

As we said above, the sources of phraseology can be:

1. biblicalisms: bread upon the waters (Ecclesiastes 11:1. "Cast thy bread upon the waters: for thou shalt find it after many days." Utterance, calling to do good freely.
2. Latinisms: bread and circuses (panem et circenses, bread and circus games; a demand of the Roman mob under Emperor Augustus).
3. mythologisms: sayings based on mythology and fairy tales. Examples: Lucullian banquet (A lavish feast named after the ancient Roman rich man Lucullus, famous for his extraordinary luxury);
4. Other languages: appetite comes with eating; (from the French "l'appetit vient en mangeant" - appetite comes with eating); you are what you eat (from German Der Mensch ist, was er ißt - a man is what he eats (L. Feuerbach).
5. Film and media: "Be my guest!" - is the title of a song from the musical cartoon "Beauty and the Beast.

Again, the relevance of a phraseology can be checked. An online corpus, an Internet search, or an associative survey of native speakers are appropriate methods for this purpose.

Having analyzed English dictionaries, we came to the following conclusion: English hospitality carries with it an element of friendliness on the part of the host and commitment in treating and entertaining. Moreover, this concept also has a business connotations, which does not exist in Russian hospitality.

We have considered the representation of the concept "hospitality" in Russian and English linguocultures.

The analysis of lexicographic sources and the highlighted key semes made it possible to determine the components that represent the concept "hospitality" in English- and Russian-

speaking linguocultures.

Thus, in the Russian linguistic culture, hospitality is a fragment of the autostereotype of the Russian people, the core lexeme "hospitality" has ability to create polysemic expressions and phraseological expressions. The key semes of the Russian concept are hospitality and hospitable [28]. Hospitality reflects manifestations of love, care and constant readiness to receive guests; this concept is also associated with treats and unselfishness. Negative aspects of the concept are not so pronounced. Recently, the component "status behavior", "demonstration of status" has been associated with hospitality. However, this element is not so clearly expressed.

In the English linguistic culture hospitality is also predominantly colored, the negative component is manifested in the phraseological units, reflecting the attitude towards an unwanted guest. The distinctive components of the concept "hospitality" in the English linguoculture, according to the analysis carried out, the components of respectfulness and entertainment of the guest. The key semes, according to the dictionary definitions, are friendliness and generosity. Sometimes there is a component of pretense in relation to an unwanted or too delayed guest. Pretense is more approved behavior than rudeness and impoliteness. However, in the younger generations, however, sincerity is valued above diplomacy. Reception of guests is more ritualized. The invitation, adherence to tradition, the dress code and the procedure of seeing the guest off are significant.

All said leads to the following conclusions:

1. The key elements of each linguistic culture can and should be studied in the form of concepts, including in this sphere not only logical components of the concept, but also evaluative, associative, subjective-emotional components.
2. The concept "hospitality" is one of the key concepts in any linguistic culture and is a part of a broader conceptsphere of a stranger.
3. In the Russian and English versions of the concept "hospitality" common elements prevail. The main differences are the greater emphasis on hospitality in Russian culture and less emotional load and emphasis on respect in the English culture.
4. The core of the concept in both cultures does not change over time, but the periphery can lose some elements and gain others. All said that the concept "hospitality" in both cultures requires constant monitoring and further study.

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